

Multiproducts by integrating mechanical wood processing and cascading of by-products

Integrated multi-production maximizes resource efficiency of wood raw material use by combining effectively side streams from the core business with co-production. Production plants are operating in the same compact industrial area, which brings synergies to processes and reduces costs and emissions of sawmill internal logistics. Bioenergy accounts for 98% of heat production. Chips from logging residues and wood processing by-products are used as fuel for own production plants and are sold to regional power plants. The higher-quality residue sawmill chip is sold to the pulp industry.

Regional coverage and transferability

Industrial symbiosis networks can be found in Northern Europe today. These co-production networks include wood resources also energy recovery from waste particles. They achieve high efficiency in processing. Situated in Finland today, transferability is possible in other areas of the Europe (and worldwide) where framework conditions match raw material availability. The integrated entity can adapt as needed to replace old production as new business opportunities emerge. A peculiarity is related to the fact that Finnish legislation supports cascading use in bio-energy with regional partners. A supportive legal situation of such network can help to attract such new actors.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ All materials from harvested trees are used. Production side streams, e.g. chips and sawdust, are both used in own chipboard production and/or are sold to contract customers as raw materials for pulp and energy production.
- ▶ It enables further processing of side streams into value-added wood panel products within the same company.
- ▶ It provides readiness to adapt the demand for new uses of wood (e.g., advanced biofuels, extractives and other bio-based products).
- ▶ The needed energy for own and regional use is produced in the company's biopower plant with forest chips or circulated wood chips.
- ▶ The core businesses have been diversified into sawing and plywood plus particle board manufacturing, resulting in optimal material efficiency. Direct connection to prefabricated house industry increases material efficiency in the wood construction sector.
- ▶ Optimal location of production plants in relation to the wood procurement area, optimal wood species ratio mix in the wood use at plant, and often own wood procurement are advantages for cascading use of raw materials that leads to profitable operations.